

UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI
DI MILANO

UNIVERSITÀ
DI TORINO

ivia
Institut Valencià
d'Investigacions Agràries

SWRI
Soil and Water Resources Institute

External Scientific Report

PPP exposure models for 3D orchards considering spraying technologies in Southern Europe

Giovanna Azimonti¹, Patricia Chueca Adell², Emilio Clementi¹, Konstantinos P. Ferentinos³, Cruz Garcerá Figueroa², Marco Grella⁴, Mara Luini¹, Paolo Marucco⁴, Eric Mozzanini⁴, Marco Resecco⁴, Luca Tosti¹

¹ International Centre for Pesticides and Health Risk Prevention-ASST Fatebenefratelli Sacco-
Department of Biomedical and Clinical Sciences, University of Milan, Italy.

²Centro de Agroingeniería Instituto Valenciano de Investigaciones Agrarias (IVIA), Valencia, Spain.

³Hellenic Agricultural Organization "DIMITRA" / Institute of Soil & Water Resources / Dept. of
Agricultural Engineering (ELGO-DIMITRA), Athens, Greece.

⁴University of Turin (UNITO) - Department of Agricultural, Forest and Food Sciences (DiSAFA),
Grugliasco, Italy.

Appendix E – Literature search

Table of contents

Appendix E – Literature search	3
E.1 Articles selected by title	3
E.2 Articles selected by abstract	12
E.3. Articles assessed - VINES	14
A.4. Articles assessed - OLIVES	41
A.5. Articles assessed - CITRUS	51

Appendix E – Literature search

E.1 Articles selected by title

No.	FIRST AUTHOR	PUBLICATION YEAR	TITLE
1	Abbas	2020	Different sensor based intelligent spraying systems in Agriculture
2	Alves-Cunha	2014	Field data and prediction models of pesticide spray drift on coffee crop
3	Ammar	2013	Qualitative distribution of spray drift deposit by using some ground spraying techniques on olive trees for controlling <i>Parlatoria oleae</i> (Colvee) (Hemiptera: Diaspididae)
4	Aru	2019	Investigation of spraying efficiency of an aerial spraying system in a super-high density olive grove in Greece
5	Asaei	2019	Site-specific orchard sprayer equipped with machine vision for chemical usage management
6	Balsari	2005	A system to assess the mass balance of spray applied to tree crops
7	Balsari	2013	Study of a Test Methodology to Assess Potential Drift Generated by Air-Assisted Sprayers
8	Balsari	2014	Assessment of the amount of spray drift in vineyard and in orchard in Emilia-Romagna using conventional and spray drift reducing techniques.
9	Balsari	2015	Spray drift measurements in Italian vineyards and orchards
10	Bayat	2005	An air-assisted spinning disc nozzle and its performance on spray deposition and reduction of drift potential
11	Bedos	2001	Mass transfer of pesticides into the atmosphere
12	Behmer	2009	Evaluation of low-drift nozzles in agrochemical applications in orchards
13	Benzing	2021	Appropriate sampling methods and statistics can tell apart fraud from pesticide drift in organic farming
14	Benzing	2021	Appropriate sampling methods and statistics can tell apart fraud from pesticide drift in organic farming_CORRECTION
15	Benzing	2021	Appropriate sampling methods and statistics can tell apart fraud from pesticide drift in organic farming_suplement
16	Bidleman	1999	Atmospheric transport and air-surface exchange of pesticides
17	Biglia	2022	UAV-Spray Application in Vineyards: Flight Modes and Spray System Adjustment Effects on Canopy Deposit, Coverage, and off-Target Losses
18	Biocca	2021	Evaluation of Drift-Reducing Nozzles for Pesticide Application in Hazelnut
19	Blanco	2017	Real-Time Particle Monitoring of Pesticide Drift from Two Different Orchard Sprayers_washington_seattle_THESIS
20	Blanco	2019	Real-Time Monitoring of Spray Drift from Three Different Orchard Sprayers

3D-orchards

No.	FIRST AUTHOR	PUBLICATION YEAR	TITLE
21	Blanco	2019	Real-time particle monitoring of pesticide drift from an axial fan airblast orchard sprayer
22	Bonds	2015	A Literature Review of Downwind Drift from Airblast Sprayers- Development of Standard Methodologies and a Drift Database
23	Bonds	2016	Development of a spray drift database and an example of how it has been used to observe the effects of canopy and droplet size on drift profiles in apple orchards
24	Bourodimos	2019	Development and field evaluation of a spray drift risk assessment tool for vineyard spraying application
25	Brown	2018	Measurement of pesticide drift from an unmanned aerial vehicle application to a vineyard
26	Bui	1998	Evaluation of samplers for spray drift
27	Butler Ellis	2014	Bystander and resident exposure to spray drift from orchard applications field measurements, including a comparison of spray drift collectors
28	Butler Ellis	2016	Spray drift- An investigation of the relationship between field, wind tunnel measurements and model predictions for determining drift reduction
29	Cai	1997	Evaluation of five fluorescent dyes and triethyl phosphate as atmospheric tracers of agricultural sprays
30	Canella Vieira	2021	Hooded broadcast sprayer for particle drift reduction
31	Capri	2005	Deposition and Dissipation of Chlorpyrifos in Surface Water Following Vineyard Applications in Northern Italy
32	Celen	2009	Effect of air assistance on deposition distribution on spraying by tunnel-type electrostatic sprayer
33	Charizopoulos	1999	Occurrence of pesticides in rain of the Axios River Basin, Greece
34	Chen	2013	Spray drift and off-target loss reductions with a precision air-assisted sprayer
35	Chen	2021	Research advances of the drift reducing technologies in application of agricultural aviation spraying
36	Coscollà	2014	Particle size distributions of currently used pesticides in ambient air of an agricultural Mediterranean area
37	Cross	2001	Spray deposits and losses in different sized apple trees from an axial fan orchard sprayer 1. Effects of spray liquid flow rate
38	Cross	2001	Spray deposits and losses in different sized apple trees from an axial fan orchard sprayer 2. Effects of spray quality
39	Cross	2002	Efficacy of drift-reducing orchard spraying methods
40	Cross	2003	Spray deposits and losses in different sized apple trees from an axial fan orchard sprayer 3. Effects of air volumetric flow rate

3D-orchards

No.	FIRST AUTHOR	PUBLICATION YEAR	TITLE
41	Cunha	2012	Risk assessment of pesticide spray drift from citrus applications with air-blast sprayers in Spain
42	Da Silva	2006	A Lagrangian model for spray behaviour within vine canopies
43	De Schampheleire	2005	The assesment of spray drift damage for ten major crops in Belgium
44	De Schampheleire	2007	Risk assessment of pesticide spray drift damage in Belgium
45	De Schampheleire	2009	Deposition of spray drift behind border structures
46	De Schampheleire	2009	Effects on pesticide spray drift of the physicochemical properties of the spray liquid
47	Dekeyser	2014	Spray deposition assessment using different application techniques in artificial orchard trees
48	Derksen	2006	Effect of Application Variables on Spray Deposition, Coverage, and Ground Losses in Nursery Tree Applications
49	Derksen	2007	Coverage and drift produced by air induction and conventional hydraulic nozzles used for orchard applications
50	Derksen	1999	Influence of hooded and air-assist vineyard applications on plant and worker protection
51	Di Prinzio	2010	Effect of pressure on the quality of pesticide applications in orchards
52	Donkersley	2011	A meta-analysis of spray drift sampling
53	Doruchowski	2009	Precise spray application in fruit growing accord
54	Doruchowski	2011	Automatically controlled sprayer to implement spray drift reducing application strategies in orchards
55	Doruchowski	2013	Drift evaluation tool to raise awareness and support training on the sustainable use of pesticides by drift mitigation
56	Ellis	2010	A spray drift model for assessment of ground deposits from boom sprayers
57	EPA	1998	EPA-HQ-OPPT-2009-0153-0004 Spray Drift Field Deposition
58	EPA	1999	downwind deposition tolerance bounds for orchards
59	EUROPOEM I	1996	Draft final report appendices
60	EUROPOEM I	1996	Draft final report
61	EUROPOEM II	2002	Bystander Working Group Report
62	Fornasiero	2017	Effect of spray drift reduction techniques on pests and predatory mites in orchards and vineyards
63	Fox	2000	Drift from spraying orchards
64	Ganzelmeier	1995	Studies on the spray drift of plant protection products
65	Ganzelmeier	2000	Drift, drift reducing sprayers and sprayer testing
66	Ganzelmeier	2002	Pesticide application and minimisation of environment impact
67	Ganzelmeier	2004	Testing of plant protection equipment in Germany

3D-orchards

No.	FIRST AUTHOR	PUBLICATION YEAR	TITLE
68	Garcerá	2017	Spray pesticide applications in Mediterranean citrus orchards: Canopy deposition and off-target losses
69	Gaskin	2006	Adjuvant and application technologies to minimise off-target drift from kiwifruit sprays
70	Geert	1998	Buffer Zones for Reducing Pesticide Drift to Ditches and Risks to Aquatic Organisms
71	Geoghegan	2014	Testing flow-through air samplers for use in near-field vapour drift studies by measuring pyrimethanil in air after spraying
72	Gil	2013	Development of Two Portable Patternators to Improve Drift Control and Operator Training in the Operation of Vineyard Sprayers
73	Gil	2013	Use of a Terrestrial LIDAR Sensor for Drift Detection in Vineyard Spraying
74	Gil	2018	First attempts to obtain a reference drift curve for traditional olive grove's plantations following ISO 22866
75	Gil	2005	Emission of pesticides to the air during sprayer application-A bibliographic review
76	Gil Y	2005	Methodology for Assessment of Drift from Radial Sprayers in Vineyard Applications
77	Gil	2007	Atmospheric loss of pesticides above an artificial vineyard during air-assisted spraying
78	Gil	2007	Caractérisation expérimentale des émissions de pesticides vers l'air pendant les pulvérisations viticoles_ Memoire THESIS
79	Gil	2008	Influence of micrometeorological factors on pesticide loss to the air during vine spraying: data analysis with statistical and fuzzy inference models
80	Glotfelty	1990	Studies of the distribution, drift, and volatilization of diazinon resulting from spray application to a dormant peach orchard
81	Godoy-Nieto	2022	Assessment of Spray Deposit and Loss in Traditional and Intensive Olive Orchards with Conventional and Crop-Adapted Sprayers
82	Gregorio	2019	Assessment of spray drift potential reduction for hollow-cone nozzles: Part 2. LiDAR technique
83	Grella	2016	Effect of sprayer settings on spray drift during pesticide application in poplar plantations
84	Grella	2017	Advances in developing a new test method to assess spray drift potential from air blast sprayers
85	Grella	2017	Ground Deposition and Airborne Spray Drift Assessment in Vineyard and Orchard- The Influence of environmental Variables and Sprayer Settings
86	Grella	2019	Toward a new method to classify the airblast sprayers according to their potential drift reduction- comparison of direct and new indirect measurement methods

3D-orchards

No.	FIRST AUTHOR	PUBLICATION YEAR	TITLE
87	Grella	2020	Development of Drift-Reducing Spouts For Vineyard Pneumatic Sprayers Measurement of Droplet Size Spectra Generated and Their Classification
88	Grella	2020	Spray Drift Generated in Vineyard during Under-Row Weed Control and Suckering Evaluation of Direct and Indirect Drift-Reducing Techniques
89	Grella	2022	Environmental Evaluation of Vineyard Airblast Sprayers Through a Comprehensive Spray Mass-Balance Approach
90	Grella	2023	Assessment of fine droplets (10 µm) in primary airborne spray drift A new methodological approach
91	Hahn	2014	Characterization of Field Margins in Intensified Agro-Ecosystems—Why Narrow Margins Should Matter in Terrestrial Pesticide Risk Assessment and Management
92	Hamey	2008	Current approaches and knowledge with a view to develop a Guidance Document for pesticide exposure assessment for workers, operators, bystanders and reside
93	Heijne	2002	Air inclusion nozzles don't reduce pollution of surface water during orchard spraying in the Netherlands
94	Heinkel	2001	Application of new fungicides with drift reducing injector nozzles in viticulture.doc
95	Herbst	2001	A Method to Determine Spray Drift Potential from Nozzles and Its Link to Buffer Zone Restrictions
96	Holland	1997	Drift from orchard spraying
97	Holterman	2014	Developing a generic model for spray drift in fruit crop spraying
98	Holterman	2016	Development of a spray drift model for pesticide applications in fruit orchards
99	Holterman	2016	Modelling the exposure of water bodies to spray drift for fruit growing in the Netherlands
100	Holterman	2018	development of a spray drift model for spray appl in orchards
101	Holterman	2021	WUR Drift Calculator user manual Belonging to software version 2.6
102	Homer	2020	Spray drift with several nozzles under wind breeze in a vineyard nursery
103	Jensen	2014	Spray mass balance in pesticide application A review
104	Jiang	2023	Factors Affecting Droplet Loss behind Canopies with Air-Assisted Sprayers Used for Fruit Trees
105	Johnson	2021	SDTF Development of Data and Models for Determining Off-Target Drift of Agricultural Pesticides
106	Kasiotis	2014	Spray drift reduction under Southern European conditions: A pilot study in the ECOPEST Project in Greece
107	Kasiotis	2014	Spray drift reduction under southern european conditions: a pilot study in the Ecopest project in Greece
108	Kasner	2018	Spray Drift from a Conventional Axial Fan Airblast Sprayer in a Modern Orchard Work Environment+supplementary_material

3D-orchards

No.	FIRST AUTHOR	PUBLICATION YEAR	TITLE
109	Kasner	2020	Spray Drift from Three Airblast Sprayer Technologies in a Modern Orchard Work Environment+supplementary_material
110	Knewitz	2002	Drift-reducing spray application in orchards and biological efficacy of pesticides
111	Koch	2004	Comparison of dose response of pesticide spray deposits versus drift deposits
112	Koch	2004	The patchiness of pesticide drift deposition patterns in plant canopies
113	Koch	2005	Aspects of wind measurement and the effect of wind on transport and deposition of drift particles during pesticide application
114	Koch	2008	Methodology and sampling technique of spray deposit and distribution measurement in vineyards
115	Koch	2009	Implementing drift reduction technology into risk assessment and practical advice for farmers and growers
116	Kruckeberg	2012	The relative accuracy of driftsim when used as a real-time spray drift predictor
117	Landers	2001	Improving Deposition and reducing drift in orchards
118	Landers	2011	Improving-Spray-Deposition-And-Reducing-Drift---Airflow-Adjustment-Is-The-Answer
119	Larb	2022	Evaluation of Downwind Spray Drift from Airblast Spray Applications in Almond, Citrus, and Grape
120	Larbi	2021	Spray Drift Study in Citrus to Support Orchard and Vineyard airblast drift modelling effort
121	Lazzaro	2008	Role of hedgerows in intercepting spray drift Evaluation and modelling of the effects
122	Lefrancq	2013	Kresoxim methyl deposition, drift and runoff in a vineyard catchment
123	Lloyd	1987	Orchard sprayers-comparative operator exposure and spray drift study
124	Mahmud	2021	Opportunities and Possibilities of Developing an Advanced Precision Spraying System for Tree Fruits
125	Markle	2016	Evaluation of spray application methods for navel orangeworm control in almonds
126	Mcartney	2008	Comparative Performance of Air-induction and conventional nozzles on an axial fan sprayer in medium density apple orchards
127	McCollom	1986	drift comparisons between aerial and ground orchard application
128	Meli	2003	Studies on pesticide spray drift in a Mediterranean citrus area
129	Meli	2007	Exposure of surface water bodies to chlorpyrifos and chlorpyrifos-methyl in the mediterranean area
130	Mercier	2020	Direct dermal and inhalation exposure of bystanders and residents during vine foliar application
131	Mescalchin	2013	Checking the distribution quality of agrochemicals in the vineyard through the use of field monitoring

3D-orchards

No.	FIRST AUTHOR	PUBLICATION YEAR	TITLE
132	Michael	2020	Influence of Spray Technology and Application Rate on Leaf Deposit and Ground Losses in Mountain Viticulture
133	Miller	2000	Atmospheric stability effects on pesticide drift from an irrigated orchard
134	Miranda Fuentes	2015	Influence of liquid-volume and airflow rates on spray application quality and homogeneity in super-intensive olive tree canopies
135	Miranda Fuentes	2016	Assessing the optimal liquid volume to be sprayed on isolated olive trees according to their canopy volumes
136	Miranda Fuentes	2017	Improving plant protection product applications in traditional and intensive olive orchards through the development of new prototype air-assisted sprayers
137	Miranda Fuentes	2018	Reducing spray drift by adapting the spraying equipment to the canopy shape in olive orchards with isolated trees
138	Miranda-Fuentes	2018	Developing Strategies to Reduce Spray Drift in Pneumatic Spraying in Vineyards: Assessment of the Parameters Affecting Droplet Size in Pneumatic Spraying
139	Morales-Rodríguez	2022	A comparison between conventional sprayers and new UAV sprayers: A study case of vineyards and olives in extremadura (Spain)
140	Moshou	2020	Assessment of genetic effects and pesticide exposure of farmers in NW Greece
141	Musiu	2019	Spray deposition and distribution on the targets and losses to the ground as affected by application volume rate, airflow rate and target position
142	Nackley	2021	Variable-rate Spray Technology Optimizes Pesticide Application by Adjusting for Seasonal Shifts in Deciduous Perennial Crops
143	Nuyttens	2008	Direct and indirect drift assessment means. Part 4: a comparative study
144	Nuyttens	2008	Direct and indirect drift assessment means. Part 3: field drift experiments
145	Nuyttens	2010	Comparison between indirect and direct spray drift assessment methods
146	Ohliger	2010	Water Body and Riparian Buffer Strip Characteristics in a Vineyard Area to Support Aquatic Pesticide Exposure Assessment
147	Ortí	2022	Preliminary Evaluation of a Blast Sprayer Controlled by Pulse-Width-Modulated Nozzles
148	Otto	2015	Spray drift reduction techniques for vineyards in fragmented landscapes
149	Otto	2018	Droplets deposition pattern from a prototype of a fixed spraying system in a sloping vineyard
150	Padovani	2004	Landscape-Level Approach To Assess Aquatic Exposure via Spray Drift for Pesticides? A Case Study in a Mediterranean Area
151	Padovani	2005	Chlorpyrifos-methyl dissipation in a small adjacent water body following application to citrus
152	Pappalardo	2022	Pesticide Contamination of Freshwater Ecosystems: Mapping Vulnerable Areas and Mitigation Scenarios in the Prosecco DOCG Wine Production Area

3D-orchards

No.	FIRST AUTHOR	PUBLICATION YEAR	TITLE
153	Pérez-Ruiz	2011	Optimization of agrochemical application in olive groves based on positioning sensor
154	Pergher G., Gubiani R., Tonetto G.	1997	Foliar deposition and pesticide losses from three air-assisted sprayers in a hedgerow vineyard
155	Polveche	2011	Effects of Nozzle Types, Windbreak and Vegetation Stage on Drift Performance Issued From an Orchard Sprayer
156	Praat	2000	The effect of canopy development and sprayer position on spray drift from a pipfruit orchard
157	Rathnayake	2021	Downwind spray drift assessment for airblast sprayer applications in a modern apple orchard system
158	Rautmann	2001	New basic drift values in the authorisation procedure for plant protection products
159	Rautmann	2001	New basic drift values in the authorisation procedure for plant protection products publicación BBA
160	Salas	2022	Use of ultrasound anemometers to study the influence of air currents generated by a sprayer with an electronic control airflow system on foliar coverage. Effect of droplet size
161	Salcedo	2015	Description of the Airflow Produced by an Air-Assisted Sprayer during Pesticide Applications to Citrus
162	Salcedo	2021	Reducing Ground and Airborne Drift Losses in Young Apple Orchards with PWM-Controlled Spray Systems
163	Salyani	1992	Drift losses from citrus spray applications
164	Salyani	1992	Spray drift from ground and aerial applications
165	Salyani	2004	Drift potential of citrus air-carrier sprayers
166	Salyani	2007	Mass Balance of Citrus Spray Applications
167	Salyani	2013	Effects of sprayer operating parameters on airborne drift from citrus air-carrier sprayers
168	SDTF	1997	A summary of airblast application studies
169	SDTF	1999	Background Document for the Scientific Advisory Panel on Orchard Airblast Downwind Deposition Tolerance Bounds for Orchards
170	Sinha	2019	Drift Potential from a Solid Set Canopy Delivery System and an Axial-Fan Air-Assisted Sprayer during Applications in Grapevines
171	Sinha	2020	Comparison of within Canopy Deposition for a Solid Set Canopy Delivery System (SSCDS) and an Axial-Fan Airblast Sprayer in a Vineyard
172	Soheilifard	2020	Chemical footprint of pesticides used in citrus orchards based on canopy deposition and off-target losses

3D-orchards

No.	FIRST AUTHOR	PUBLICATION YEAR	TITLE
173	Solanelles	1997	Effect of the volumetric airflow rate and sprayer speed on the reduction of spray drift losses in an Apple orchard
174	Solanelles	2002	Spray application efficiency of an electronic control system for proportional application to the canopy volume
175	Solanelles	2006	An electronic control system for pesticide application proportional to the canopy width of tree crops
176	Torrent	2017	Comparison between standard and drift reducing nozzles for pesticide application in citrus. Part I. Effects on wind tunnel and field spray drift
177	Torrent	2020	Determination of spray drift and buffer zones in 3D crops using the ISO standard and new LiDAR methodologies
178	Van Steenwyk	2020	Spray drift mitigation using opposing synchronized air-blast sprayers
179	Vercruyssen	1999	Off target ground deposits from spraying a semi-dwarf orchard
180	Vischetti	2008	Measures to reduce pesticide spray drift in a small aquatic ecosystem in vineyard estate
181	Wang	2021	Assessment of Spray Deposition, Drift and Mass Balance from Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Sprayer Using an Artificial Vineyard
182	Wang G.	2020	Field evaluation of spray drift and environmental impact using an agricultural unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) sprayer
183	Wang J.	2019	Meteorological and flight altitude effects on deposition, penetration, and drift in pineapple aerial spraying
184	Warneke	2019	Sensor Sprayers for Specialty Crop Production
185	Wenneker	2005	Effect of air induction nozzle (coarse droplet), air assistance and one-sided spraying of the outer tree row
186	Willenbockel	2022	A Critical Scoping Review of Pesticide Exposure Biomonitoring Studies in Overhead Cultures
187	Wilson	2004	Minimizing direct deposition of pesticides into waterways associated with Indian River citrus production
188	Zande	2008	Nozzle Classification for Drift Reduction in Orchard Spraying
189	Zande	2010	Risk estimation of bystander and residential exposure from orchard spraying based on measured spray drift data
190	Zande	2012	Nozzle classification for drift reduction in orchard spraying
191	Zande	2014	Spray drift and bystander risk from fruit crop spraying
192	Zande	2015	Spray drift and resident risk in orchard spraying reference and spray drift reducing techniques
193	Zivan	2017	Primary and secondary pesticide drift profiles from a peach orchard

3D-orchards

E.2 Articles selected by abstract

No.	FIRST AUTHOR	PUBLICATION YEAR	TITLE
1	Godoy-Nieto	2022	Assessment of Spray Deposit and Loss in Traditional and Intensive Olive Orchards with Conventional and Crop-Adapted Sprayers
2	Miranda Fuentes	2018	Reducing spray drift by adapting the spraying equipment to the canopy shape in olive orchards with isolated trees
3	Solanelles	2006	An electronic control system for pesticide application proportional to the canopy width of tree crops
4	Solanelles	2002	Spray application efficiency of an electronic control system for proportional application to the canopy volume
5	Bourodimos	2019	Development and field evaluation of a spray drift risk assessment tool for vineyard spraying application
6	Kasiotis	2014	Spray drift reduction under Southern European conditions: A pilot study in the Ecopest Project in Greece
7	Ahrens	2023	Development of a method for measuring exposure of residents and bystanders following high crop application of plant protection products
8	Balsari	2014	Assessment of the amount of spray drift in vineyard and in orchard in Emilia-Romagna using conventional and spray drift reducing techniques.
9	Bourodimos	2019	Development and Field Evaluation of a Spray Drift Risk Assessment Tool for Vineyard Spraying Application
10	Glaser	2023	A model canopy for spray drift measurements in orchards
11	Herbst	2023	Spray drift from application of plant protection products with drones in vineyards
12	Wang	2021	Assessment of Spray Deposition, Drift and Mass Balance from Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Sprayer Using an Artificial Vineyard
13	Celen	2009	Effect of air assistance on deposition distribution on spraying by tunnel-type electrostatic sprayer
14	Derksen	1999	Influence of hooded and air-assist vineyard applications on plant and worker protection
15	Garcerá.	2017	Spray pesticide applications in Mediterranean citrus orchards: Canopy deposition and off-target losses
16	Mescalchin	2013	Checking the distribution quality of agrochemicals in the vineyard through the use of field monitoring
17	Balsari	2015	Spray drift measurements in Italian vineyards and orchards
18	Biocca	2021	Evaluation of Drift-Reducing Nozzles for Pesticide Application in Hazelnut
19	Bourodimos	2019	Development and Field Evaluation of a Spray Drift Risk Assessment Tool for Vineyard Spraying Application
20	Fornasiero	2017	Effect of spray drift reduction techniques on pests and predatory mites in orchards and vineyards

3D-orchards

21	Gil	2018	First attempts to obtain a reference drift curve for traditional olive grove's plantations following ISO 22866
22	Gil	2005	Methodology for Assessment of Drift from Radial Sprayers in Vineyard Applications
23	Grella	2016	Effect of sprayer settings on spray drift during pesticide application in poplar plantations
24	Grella	2017	Ground Deposition and Airborne Spray Drift Assessment in Vineyard and Orchard- The Influence of environmental Variables and Sprayer Settings
25	Grella	2019	Toward a new method to classify the airblast sprayers according to their potential drift reduction- comparison of direct and new indirect measurement methods
26	Grella	2023	Assessment of fine droplets (10 µm) in primary airborne spray drift A new methodological approach
27	Lefrancq	2013	Kresoxim methyl deposition, drift and runoff in a vineyard catchment
28	Meli	2003	Studies on pesticide spray drift in a Mediterranean citrus area
29	Meli	2007	exposure of surface water bodies to chlorpyrifos and chlorpyrifos-methyl in the mediterranean area
30	Padovani	2004	Landscape-Level Approach To Assess Aquatic Exposure via Spray Drift for Pesticides? A Case Study in a Mediterranean Area
31	Padovani	2005	Chlorpyrifos-methyl dissipation in a small adjacent water body following application to citrus
32	Torrent	2017	Comparison between standard and drift reducing nozzles for pesticide application in citrus. Part I. Effects on wind tunnel and field spray drift
33	Torrent	2020	Determination of spray drift and buffer zones in 3D crops using the ISO standard and new LiDAR methodologies
34	Vischetti	2008	Measures to reduce pesticide spray drift in a small aquatic ecosystem in vineyard estate
35	Mercier	2020	Direct dermal and inhalation exposure of bystanders and residents during vine foliar application

E.3. Articles assessed - VINES

Title		Ground Deposition and Airborne Spray Drift Assessment in Vineyard and Orchard: The Influence of Environmental Variables and Sprayer Settings			
Authors		Marco Grella, Montserrat Gallart, Paolo Marucco, Paolo Balsari and Emilio Gil			
Reference		<i>Sustainability</i> 2017 . 9(5), 728			
DOI		https://doi.org/10.3390/su9050728			
Country		Spain	Spain		
Orchard characteristics	Crop	Vineyard	Orchard		
	Cultivar	Tempranillo	Apple tree orchard cv. Golden delicious		
	Row direction	N-E	N-E		
	Row x Tree spacing (m)	2,8 x 1,2	4 x 1,2		
	Total height (m)	1,6	3,4		
	Skirt (m)				
	Tree height (m)	0,8			
	Diameter 1 (m)				
	Diameter 2 (m)				
	Canopy volume (m ³)				
	TRV (m ³ TRV/ha)				
	LWA (m ² LWA/ha)				
	BBCH (vineyard)	83	81		
Foliar density/LAI....					
Meteo	Distance/Position of sensors respect the orchard		30	30	
	Height 1 (m)= 4 m. Wind conditions recorded at 4m humidity and temperature recorded at 2 and 4 m.	Frequency (Hz)	1	1	All meteo parameters were reported for each replicate in a detailed table and all parameters in every replicate accomplish iso 22866 requirement
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	✓	✓	
		Horizontal wind direction (°)	✓	✓	
Vertical wind speed (m/s)					

3D-orchards

		Temperature (°C)	✓	✓	
		Relative humidity (%)	✓	✓	
		% of measures $\geq 30^\circ$			
		% of measures $\geq 45^\circ$	✓	✓	
	Stability				
Trial layout	Length of passes (row length) (m)		60	60	
	Rows treated (number of rows/ width treated area)		8	5	
	Spray application in the 1st row				
	Substance applied (tracer, PPP,...)	Substance	Tartrazine		Tartrazine
Concentration/Dose		10 g/L		10 g/L	
Treatment/s	T1	Sprayer	Axial sprayer Dragone k2 500	Fede Qi 90 Futur 2000	
		Volume rate (L/ha)	596	932	
		Forward speed (km/h)	6	6	
		Airflow (m ³ /h)	11000	29000	
		Working pressure (MPa)	1	1,5	
		Type of nozzles	ATR 80 orange	ATR 80 red	
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	1,39	2,24	
	T2	Sprayer	Dragone k2 500	Fede Qi 90 Futur 2000	
		Volume rate (L/ha)	596	932	
		Forward speed (km/h)	6	6	
		Airflow (m ³ /h)	20000	46000	
		Working pressure (MPa)	1	1,5	
		Type of nozzles	ATR 80 orange	ATR 80 red	
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	1,39	2,24	

3D-orchards

	T3	Sprayer	Dragone k2 500	Dragone k2 500	
		Volume rate (L/ha)	626	896	
		Forward speed (km/h)	6	6	
		Airflow (m3/h)	11000	29000	
		Working pressure (MPa)	1	1,5	
		Type of nozzles	ALBUZ TVI 8002 yellow	TVI 80025 lilac	
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	1,46	2,24	
	T4	Sprayer	Dragone k2 500	Fede Qi 90 Futur 2000	
		Volume rate (L/ha)	626	896	
		Forward speed (km/h)	6	6	
		Airflow (m3/h)	20000	46000	
		Working pressure (MPa)	1	1,5	
		Type of nozzles	ALBUZ TVI 8002 yellow	TVI 80025 lilac	
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	1,46	2,24	
Response variables	Airborne drift	Collector (if lines, vertical/horizontal)	Polyethene vertical lines	Polyethene vertical lines	
		Height range (max-min measured height) (m)	0-6	0-6	
		Precision (0.5 m/ 1 m...)	0,5	0,5	
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	5/10	5/10	
		Replicates/distance	2/2	2/2	
	Collector	Petri dishes	Petri dishes		

3D-orchards

Sedimenting drift	Distance range (max-min measured distance) (m)	1/30	1/30	
	Sampler area (cm ²)	154	154	
	Distance/s to the first row (m)	1,25/31,25	1,25/31,25	
	Replicates/distance	6/10	6/10	

Notes to Grella et al. 2017:

Three replicates were carried out (each replicate at different time); according to the ISO22866:2005 weather conditions were recorded at 1Hz, and details are reported per each replicate in a dedicated table. Ten distances from applied area were sampled and at each distance 6 collectors, used as technical replicates, were placed spaced 1m distance ion between. Airborne drift was also assessed.

Data could be used to obtain drift curves.

Title	Toward a new method to classify the airblast sprayers according to their potential drift reduction: comparison of direct and new indirect measurement methods			
Authors	Marco Grella, Paolo Marucco and Paolo Balsari			
Reference	<i>Pest management science</i> , 2019 . 75(8), 2219			
DOI	https://doi.org/10.1002/ps.5354			
Country	Italy			
Orchard characteristics	Crop	Vineyard		
	Cultivar	Vermentino		
	Row direction	N-E		
	Row x Tree spacing (m)	2,8 x 0,8		
	Total height (m)	1,6		
	Skirt (m)			
	Tree height (m)	0,8		
	Diameter 1 (m)			
	Diameter 2 (m)			
	Canopy volume (m ³)			
	TRV (m ³ TRV/ha)			
LWA (m ² LWA/ha)				

3D-orchards

	BBCH (vineyard)		83		
	Foliar density/LAI...		1.9		
Meteo	Distance/Position of sensors respect the orchard		30		
	Height 1 (m)= 4 m. Wind conditions recorded at 4m humidity and temperature recorded at 2 and 4 m.	Frequency (Hz)	1		In the paper 0.1 Hz was reported but 1 Hz is correct.
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	✓		All meteo parameters were reported for each replicate in a detailed table and all parameters in every replicate accomplish iso 22866 requirement
		Horizontal wind direction (°)	✓		
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)			
		Temperature (°C)	✓		
		Relative humidity (%)	✓		
		% of measures $\geq 30^\circ$			
		% of measures $\geq 45^\circ$	✓		
Stability					
Trial layout	Length of passes (row length) (m)		60		
	Rows treated (number of rows/ width treated area)		8		
	Spray application in the 1st row		yes		
	Substance applied (tracer, PPP,...)	Substance	Tartrazine		
Concentration/Dose		10 g/L			
Treatment/s	T1	Sprayer	Axial sprayer Dragone k2 500		
		Volume rate (L/ha)	667		
		Forward speed (km/h)	6		
		Airflow (m ³ /h)	11000		
		Working pressure (MPa)	1		

3D-orchards

		Type of nozzles	ATR 80 orange		
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	1,39		
	T2	Sprayer	Dragone k2 500		
		Volume rate (L/ha)	667		
		Forward speed (km/h)	6		
		Airflow (m3/h)	20000		
		Working pressure (MPa)	1		
		Type of nozzles	ATR 80 orange		
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	1,39		
	T3	Sprayer	Dragone k2 500		
		Volume rate (L/ha)	701		
		Forward speed (km/h)	6		
		Airflow (m3/h)	11000		
		Working pressure (MPa)	1		
		Type of nozzles	ALBUZ TVI 8002 yellow		
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	1,46		
	T4	Sprayer	Dragone k2 500		
		Volume rate (L/ha)	701		
		Forward speed (km/h)	6		
		Airflow (m3/h)	20000		
Working pressure (MPa)		1			
Type of nozzles		ALBUZ TVI 8002 yellow			
Liquid flowrate (L/min)		1,46			
Response variables	Airborne drift	Collector (if lines, vertical/horizontal)			
		Height range (max-min measured height) (m)			

3D-orchards

		Precision (0.5 m/ 1 m...)				
		Distance/s to the first row (m)				
		Replicates/distance				
	Sedimenting drift	Collector	Petri dishes			
		Distance range (max-min measured distance) (m)	1/30			
		Sampler area (cm ²)	154			
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	2,25/32,25			
		Replicates/distance	6/10			

Notes to Grella *et al.* 2019:

Three replicates were carried out (each replicate at different time); according to the ISO22866:2005 weather conditions were recorded at 1Hz, and details are reported per each replicate in a dedicated table. Ten distances from applied area were sampled and at each distance 6 collectors, used as technical replicates, were placed spaced 1m distance in between.

Data could be used to obtain drift curves.

Title		Development and Field Evaluation of a Spray Drift Risk Assessment Tool for Vineyard Spraying Application
Authors		Georgios Bourdimos, Michael Koutsiaras , Vasilios Psiroukis , Athanasios Balafoutis and Spyros Fountas
Reference		<i>Agriculture</i> 2019 . 9(8), 181
DOI		https://doi.org/10.3390/agriculture9080181
Country		Greece
Orchard characteristics	Crop	Vineyard
	Cultivar	
	Row direction	N-E
	Row x Tree spacing (m)	2 x 1,6
	Total height (m)	1,1
Skirt (m)		

3D-orchards

	Tree height (m)		0,9
	Diameter 1 (m)		
	Diameter 2 (m)		
	Canopy volume (m3) (indicate calculation used)		
	TRV (m3 TRV/ha)		
	LWA (m2 LWA/ha)		
	BBCH (vineyard)		83/91
	Foliar density/LAI....		1,58/1,46
Meteo	Distance/Position of sensors respect the orchard		30
	Height 1 (m)= ??	Frequency (Hz)	1
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	✓
		Horizontal wind direction (°)	✓
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)	
		Temperature (°C)	✓
		Relative humidity (%)	✓
		% of measures ≥30°	
	% of measures ≥45°	✓	
	Stability		
Trial layout	Length of passes (row lenght) (m)		
	Rows treated (number of rows/ width treated area)		
	Spray application in the 1st row		
	Substance applied (tracer, PPP,...)	Substance	
Concentration/Dose			4 g/L
Treatment/s	Treatment	Sprayer	Air assisted sprayer, Archimedes turbo FS 1000
		Volume rate (L/ha)	434
		Forward speed (km/h)	5,8
		Airflow (m3/h)	10000
		Working pressure (MPa)	1
		Type of nozzles	Teejet TXA 8002VK
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	1,4
Response variables	Airborne drift	Collector (if lines, vertical/horizontal)	Poliethylene lines
		Height range (max-min measured height) (m)	0-6
		Precision (0.5 m/ 1 m...)	1
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	5/10/15
		Replicates/distance	2

3D-orchards

	Sedimenting drift	Collector	Filter paper
		Distance range (max-min measured distance) (m)	1/30
		Sampler area (cm ²)	368
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	2/31
		Replicates/distance	3/12

Notes to Bourodimos et al. 2019:

The trial foreseen to test a single configuration of sprayer in three different drift risk conditions (two replicates for each risk indicator level, namely low medium and high), namely three wind speed conditions. It derives that the sprayer configuration was tested in six replicates. According to the ISO22866:2005 weather conditions were recorded at 1Hz, and details are reported per each replicate in a dedicated table. Twelve distances from applied area were sampled and at each distance 3 collectors, used as technical replicates.

Data could be used to obtain drift curves.

Title		Spray drift from application of plant protection products with drones in vineyards
Authors		Andreas Herbst, Michael Glaser, Kay-Uwe Bartsch
Reference		<i>Journal of Cultivated Plants / Journal für Kulturpflanzen.</i> 2023. 75(5/6), 151.
DOI		doi: 10.5073/JfK.2023.05-06.04
Country		Germany
Orchard characteristics	Crop	Vineyard
	Cultivar	
	Row direction	
	Row x Tree spacing (m)	2 tree spacing not specified
	Total height (m)	2/2,2
	Skirt (m)	
	Tree height (m)	
	Diameter 1 (m)	
	Diameter 2 (m)	
	Canopy volume (m3) (indicate calculation used)	
	TRV (m3 TRV/ha)	
LWA (m2 LWA/ha)		
BBCH (vineyard)	71 to 95	

3D-orchards

	Foliar density/LAI...		
Meteo	Distance/Position of sensors respect the orchard		20
	Height 1 (m)= 3 m	Frequency (Hz)	1
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	✓
		Horizontal wind direction (°)	✓
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)	
		Temperature (°C)	✓
		Relative humidity (%)	✓
		% of measures $\geq 30^\circ$	
Stability			
Trial layout	Length of passes (row length) (m)		20
	Rows treated (number of rows/ width treated area)		
	Spray application in the 1st row		
	Substance applied (tracer, PPP,...)	Substance	
Concentration/Dose			Brilliant Sulfoflavine 4 g/L (for trial 1 to 7); Pyranine 120% for trial 9 at 5 g/L; 8 g/L for trial 8
Treatment/s	Treatment	Sprayer	octocopter drone, MG-1S
		Volume rate (L/ha)	70,8
		Forward speed (km/h)	9
		Airflow (m ³ /h)	
		Working pressure (MPa)	0,24
		Type of nozzles	Airmix 110-015
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	1,08
		Flight height (m) (above canopy)	1
	Flight orientation	longitudinal	
	Swath width (m)	2	
	Treatment	Sprayer	octocopter drone, MG-1S
		Volume rate (L/ha)	72,1
		Forward speed (km/h)	9
		Airflow (m ³ /h)	
		Working pressure (MPa)	0,24
		Type of nozzles	XR 110-015
Liquid flowrate (L/min)		1,1	
Flight height (m) (above canopy)		1	
Flight orientation	longitudinal		
Swath width (m)	2		

3D-orchards

	Treatment	Sprayer	octocopter drone, MG-1P		
		Volume rate (L/ha)	75,2		
		Forward speed (km/h)	6,6		
		Airflow (m3/h)			
		Working pressure (MPa)	0,1		
		Type of nozzles	IDK 90-025		
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	0,6		
		Flight hight (m) (above canopy)	2,0		
		Flight orientation	Lateral		
		Swath width (m)	3,0		
		Treatment	Treatment	Sprayer	octocopter drone, MG-1P
				Volume rate (L/ha)	75,0
Forward speed (km/h)	4,8				
Airflow (m3/h)					
Working pressure (MPa)	0,4				
Type of nozzles	XR 110-010				
Liquid flowrate (L/min)	0,5				
Flight hight (m) (above canopy)	2				
Flight orientation	Lateral				
Swath width (m)	3				
Treatment	Treatment			Sprayer	octocopter drone, T16
				Volume rate (L/ha)	75
		Forward speed (km/h)	12,8		
		Airflow (m3/h)			
		Working pressure (MPa)	0,11		
		Type of nozzles	IDK 90-025		
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	0,6		
		Flight hight (m) (above canopy)	2		
		Flight orientation	Lateral		
		Swath width (m)	3		
		Treatment	Treatment	Sprayer	octocopter drone, T16
				Volume rate (L/ha)	75
Forward speed (km/h)	9,6				
Airflow (m3/h)					
Working pressure (MPa)	0,4				
Type of nozzles	XR 110-01				
Liquid flowrate (L/min)	0,45				
Flight hight (m) (above canopy)	2				

3D-orchards

	Treatment	Flight orientation	Lateral
		Swath width (m)	3
		Sprayer	octocopter drone, T16
		Volume rate (L/ha)	75
		Forward speed (km/h)	12,8
		Airflow (m3/h)	
		Working pressure (MPa)	0,11
		Type of nozzles	IDK 90-025
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	0,6
		Flight hight (m) (above canopy)	2
		Flight orientation	longitudinal
	Swath width (m)	3	
	Treatment	Sprayer	octocopter drone, MG-1S
		Volume rate (L/ha)	74,1
		Forward speed (km/h)	5,4
		Airflow (m3/h)	
		Working pressure (MPa)	0,21
		Type of nozzles	Airmix 110-015
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	0,5
		Flight hight (m) (above canopy)	2
		Flight orientation	lateral
		Swath width (m)	3
		Treatment	Sprayer
	Volume rate (L/ha)		75,4
	Forward speed (km/h)		7,6
	Airflow (m3/h)		
	Working pressure (MPa)		0,3
Type of nozzles	ATR brown		
Liquid flowrate (L/min)	0,38		
Flight hight (m) (above canopy)	1		
Flight orientation	longitudinal		
Swath width (m)	2		
Response variables	Airborne drift		Collector (if lines, vertical/horizontal)
		Height range (max-min measured height) (m)	
		Precision (0.5 m/ 1 m...)	
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	

3D-orchards

	Sedimenting drift	Replicates/distance	
		Collector	Petri dishes
		Distance range (max-min measured distance) (m)	3/20
		Sampler area (cm ²)	165
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	4/21
		Replicates/distance	10/5

Notes to Herbst *et al.* 2023:

The trial have been conducted in two different vineyard. In the first one the rows were oriented from north to south. In the second one the rows were oriented NW to SE.

10 are the replicate at each distance. 5 are the total number of distances. The replicate on each distance were spaced 1m from each other.

These data could not be used to obtain drift curves.

Title		Assessment of fine droplets (<10 µm) in primary airborne spray drift: A new methodological approach
Authors		M. Grella , J. Maffia, E. Dinuccio, P. Balsari, A. Miranda-Fuentes, P. Marucco, F. Gioelli
Reference		<i>Journal of aerosol science</i> , 2023 . 169
DOI		https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaerosci.2023.106138
Country		Italy
Orchard characteristics	Crop	Meadow
	Cultivar	
	Row direction	Passages perpendicular to theoretical N-S according to the positioned anemometers
	Row x Tree spacing (m)	
	Total height (m)	
	Skirt (m)	
	Tree height (m)	
	Diameter 1 (m)	
	Diameter 2 (m)	
	Canopy volume (m ³) (indicate calculation used)	
	TRV (m ³ TRV/ha)	
LWA (m ² LWA/ha)		

3D-orchards

	BBCH (vineyard)			
	Foliar density/LAI....			
Meteo	Distance/Position of sensors respect the orchard	30		
	Height 1 (m)= Wind conditions recorded at 3 m humidity and temperature recorded at 2 and 4 m.	Frequency (Hz)	10	
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	✓	
		Horizontal wind direction (°)	✓	
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)	✓	
		Temperature (°C)	✓	
		Relative humidity (%)	✓	
		% of measures $\geq 30^\circ$		
		% of measures $\geq 45^\circ$	✓	
Stability				
Trial layout	Length of passes (row length) (m)	60		
	Rows treated (number of rows/ width treated area)	1		
	Spray application in the 1st row			
	Substance applied (tracer, PPP,...)	Substance Concentration/Dose	Pure water	
Treatment/s	Treatment 1 (3 replicate)	Sprayer	Tower shaped, air assisted Dragone k2 500	
		Volume rate (L/ha)	262	
		Forward speed (km/h)	5,5	
		Airflow (m ³ /h)	20000	
		Working pressure (MPa)	1	
		Type of nozzles	ATR 80 lilac	
	Treatment 2 (3 replicate)	Sprayer	Tower shaped, air assisted Dragone k2 500	
		Volume rate (L/ha)	272	
		Forward speed (km/h)	5,5	
		Airflow (m ³ /h)	20000	
		Working pressure (MPa)	0,9	
		Type of nozzles	TVI 80 0075	
	Treatment 3 (3 replicate)	Sprayer	Tower shaped, air assisted Dragone k2 500	
		Volume rate (L/ha)	0	
		Forward speed (km/h)	0	
Airflow (m ³ /h)		20000		
Working pressure (MPa)		0		
	Type of nozzles	0		

3D-orchards

Response variables	Airborne drift	Liquid flowrate (L/min)	0	
		Collector (if lines, vertical/horizontal)	GRIMM 1-D optical counter	
		Height range (max-min measured height) (m)	1,5m	
		Precision (0.5 m/ 1 m...)	Punctual	
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	5/30	
		Replicates/distance	Continuative measurement during each trials/6 distances	
	Sedimenting drift	Collector		
		Distance range (max-min measured distance) (m)		
		Precision (1 m...)		
		Distance/s to the first row (m)		
		Replicates/distance		

Notes to Grella et al. 2023:

Volume rate is theoretical calculated with a 2,5m inter-row distance.

The Fan Only served as the control to eliminate the presence of fan-induced soil particles.

These data could not be used to obtain drift curves.

Title		Kresoxim methyl deposition, drift and runoff in a vineyard catchment
Authors		M. Lefrancq, G. Imfeld, S. Payraudeau, M. Millet
Reference		<i>The Science of the Total Environment</i> . 2013 . 442, 503
DOI		https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2012.09.082
Country		France
Orchard characteristics	Crop	Vineyard
	Cultivar	
	Row direction	
	Row x Tree spacing (m)	
	Total height (m)	

3D-orchards

	Skirt (m)			
	Tree height (m)			
	Diameter 1 (m)			
	Diameter 2 (m)			
	Canopy volume (m3) (indicate calculation used)			
	TRV (m3 TRV/ha)			
	LWA (m2 LWA/ha)			
	BBCH (vineyard)			
	Foliar density/LAI...			
Meteo	Distance/Position of sensors respect the orchard			
	Height 1 (m)= ??	Frequency (Hz)		
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	✓	
		Horizontal wind direction (°)		
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)		
		Temperature (°C)	✓	
		Relative humidity (%)	✓	
		% of measures ≥30°		
		% of measures ≥45°		
Stability				
Trial layout	Length of passes (row length) (m)			
	Rows treated (number of rows/ width treated area)			
	Spray application in the 1st row			
	Substance applied (tracer, PPP,...)	Substance	Kresoxim methyl deposition	
		Concentration/Dose	0,08 kg/ha	
Treatments	Treatment 1	Sprayer	"Dragged sprayer"	
		Volume rate (L/ha)		
		Forward speed (km/h)	5 to 6	

3D-orchards

		Airflow (m ³ /h)	
		Working pressure (MPa)	0,85
		Type of nozzles	
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	
Response variables	Airborne drift	Collector (if lines, vertical/horizontal)	
		Height range (max-min measured height) (m)	
		Precision (0.5 m/ 1 m...)	
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	
		Replicates/distance	
	Sedimenting drift	Collector	Petri dishes
		Distance range (max-min measured distance) (m)	
		Sampler area (cm ²)	176,71
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	
		Replicates/distance	

Notes to Lefrancq *et al.* 2013:

The test was performed in 42,7 ha vineyard catchment. The vineyard characteristics are not reported
The proper type of sprayer is unclear but in the picture it's reported an airblast sprayer
51 petri dishes located according to a differential global positioning system. Nine dishes were inside the sprayed area. In the eastern part of each plot strip were located two petri. In the western part of each plot one one petri was positioned. At the catchment outlet runoff discharge were monitored.

These data could not be used to obtain drift curves.

Title	Spray drift measurements in Italian vineyards and orchards
Authors	P. Balsari, P. Marucco, M. Grella, S. Savoia
Reference	SuproFruit 2015 – 13 th Workshop on Spray Application in Fruit Growing, Lindau, Germany, 15. – 18. July 2015
DOI	

3D-orchards

Country		Italy		
Orchard characteristics	Crop	Vineyard		
	Cultivar	Barbera		
	Row direction			
	Row x Tree spacing (m)			
	Total height (m)			
	Skirt (m)			
	Tree height (m)			
	Diameter 1 (m)			
	Diameter 2 (m)			
	Canopy volume (m3) (indicate calculation used)			
	TRV (m3 TRV/ha)			
	LWA (m2 LWA/ha)			
	BBCH (vineyard)	69/91		
	Foliar density/LAI...			
Meteo	Distance/Position of sensors respect the orchard			
	Height 1 (m)= not reported	Frequency (Hz)		
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	✓	
		Horizontal wind direction (°)	✓	
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)		
		Temperature (°C)	✓	
		Relative humidity (%)	✓	
		% of measures ≥30°		
		% of measures ≥45°	✓	
Stability				
Trial layout	Length of passes (row length) (m)			
	Rows treated (number of rows/ width treated area)			
	Spray application in the 1st row			
	Substance applied (tracer, PPP,...)	Substance	Tartrazine	
Concentration/Dose				
Treatments	Treatment 1	Sprayer	Tower shaped air assisted sprayer	
		Volume rate (L/ha)		
		Forward speed (km/h)		
		Airflow (m3/h)		
		Working pressure (MPa)		
		Type of nozzles		
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)		

3D-orchards

Response variables	Airborne drift	Collector (if lines, vertical/horizontal)	
		Height range (max-min measured height) (m)	
		Precision (0.5 m/ 1 m...)	
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	
		Replicates/distance	
	Sedimenting drift	Collector	Petri dishes
		Distance range (max-min measured distance) (m)	
		Precision (1 m...)	
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	
		Replicates/distance	

Notes to Balsari et al. 2015:

In the paper is reported that 8 different configuration have been tested for both BBCH stages.

These data could not be used to obtain drift curves.

Title		Direct dermal and inhalation exposure of bystanders and residents during vine foliar application using sprayer equipment fitted with an anti-drift device: a comparison between measured exposure levels and existing exposure models	
Authors		Thierry Mercier	
Reference		<i>Journal of Consumer Protection and Food Safety</i> . 2020 15, 219	
DOI		https://doi.org/10.1007/s00003-020-01274-1	
Country		France-Site A	France-Site B
Orchard characteristics	Crop	Vineyard	Vineyard
	Cultivar		
	Row direction	1,9 x no information about the tree spacing	3- no information about the tree spacing
	Row x Tree spacing (m)		
	Total height (m)		
	Skirt (m)		
Tree height (m)			

3D-orchards

	Diameter 1 (m)			
	Diameter 2 (m)			
	Canopy volume (m3) (indicate calculation used)			
	TRV (m3 TRV/ha)			
	LWA (m2 LWA/ha)			
	BBCH (vineyard)	14/15	14/15	
	Foliar density/LAI....			
Meteo	Distance/Position of sensors respect the orchard			
	Height 1 (m)= ???	Frequency (Hz)		
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	✓	✓
		Horizontal wind direction (°)		
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)		
		Temperature (°C)	✓	✓
		Relative humidity (%)	✓	✓
		% of measures ≥30°		
% of measures ≥45°				
	Stability			
Trial layout	Length of passes (row length) (m)			
	Rows treated (number of rows/ width treated area)			
	Spray application in the 1st row			
	Substance applied (tracer, PPP,...)	Substance	cymoxanil	cymoxanil
Concentration/Dose		1,79 g/L	1,50 g/ha	
Treatments	Treatment 1	Sprayer	Berthoud AB MOST NG	Berthoud AB MOST NG
		Volume rate (L/ha)	66	84
		Forward speed (km/h)		
		Airflow (m3/h)		
		Working pressure (MPa)		
		Type of nozzles	Lechler IDK 90	Lechler IDK 90
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)		
Response variables	Airborne drift	Collector (if lines, vertical/horizontal)	Manequin	Manequin
		Height range (max-min measured height) (m)	1,8/0,90	1,8/0,90
		Precision (0.5 m/ 1 m...)		
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	3/5/10	3/5/10
		Replicates/distance	6 replicates at 3 ad 10 m; 8 replicates at 5 m	6 replicates at 3 ad 10 m; 8 replicates at 5 m
	Sedimenting drift	Collector		

3D-orchards

		Distance range (max-min measured distance) (m)		
		Precision (1 m...)		
		Distance/s to the first row (m)		
		Replicates/distance		

Notes to Mercier 2020:

The main objective of this paper is to evaluate the direct dermal and inhalation exposure of bystanders.

These data could not be used to obtain drift curves.

Title		Measures to reduce pesticide spray drift in a small aquatic ecosystem in vineyard estate		
Authors		Costantino Vischetti, Alessandra Cardinali, Elga Monaci, Marco Nicelli, Federico Ferrari, Marco Trevisan, Ettore Capri		
Reference		<i>Science of The Total Environment</i> 2008 . 389(2-3), 497		
DOI		https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2007.09.019		
Country		Italy		
Orchard characteristics	Crop	Vineyard		
	Cultivar	Sauvignon, Croatina, Barbera, Malvasia		
	Row direction			
	Row x Tree spacing (m)			
	Total height (m)			
	Skirt (m)			
	Tree height (m)			
	Diameter 1 (m)			
	Diameter 2 (m)			
	Canopy volume (m3) (indicate calculation used)			
	TRV (m3 TRV/ha)			
	LWA (m2 LWA/ha)			
	BBCH (vineyard)			
Foliar density/LAI....				
Meteo	Distance/Position of sensors respect the orchard			
	Height 1 (m)= ???	Frequency (Hz)		
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	✓	
		Horizontal wind direction (°)	✓	
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)		

3D-orchards

		Temperature (°C)	✓		
		Relative humidity (%)	✓		
		% of measures $\geq 30^\circ$			
		% of measures $\geq 45^\circ$			
	Stability				
Trial layout	Length of passes (row length) (m)				
	Rows treated (number of rows/ width treated area)				
	Spray application in the 1st row				
	Substance applied (tracer, PPP,...)	Substance	Chlorpyrifos (C) and Metalaxyl (M)		
	Concentration/Dose	C=446 g/kg M= 75 g/kg			
Treatments	Treatment 1	Sprayer	Martignani KWH		
		Volume rate (L/ha)			
		Forward speed (km/h)			
		Airflow (m ³ /h)			
		Working pressure (MPa)	0,1013		
		Type of nozzles			
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)			
Response variables	Airborne drift	Collector (if lines, vertical/horizontal)			
		Height range (max-min measured height) (m)			
		Precision (0.5 m/ 1 m...)			
		Distance/s to the first row (m)			
		Replicates/distance			
			Pond	Protected area	
	Sedimenting drift	Collector	Drift traps. Chromatography paper		Drift traps. Chromatography paper
		Distance range (max-min measured distance) (m)	12-18		3 /24
		Dimension (m)	0,5 x 0,1		0,5 x 0,1 m
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	12/18 m		3/24
		Replicates/distance	10/4		6/9

3D-orchards

Notes to Vischetti *et al.* 2008:

In the middle of the vineyard there was a pond, that was encircled by a protected area of 10 m. On the northern and southern sides there were rows of *Populus albas* with a LAD of 0.5 m²/m³.

The application were conducted from north to south along the main wind direction

Drift traps were collected both on the pond and on the surrounding area, for the two pesticides sprayed. Each drift trap consisted on two replicates.

6 are the replicate at each distance.

9 are the total number of distances.

These data could not be used to obtain drift curves.

Title		Assessment of the amount of spray drift in vineyard and in orchard in Emilia-Romagna using conventional and spray drift reducing techniques.	
Authors		Balsari, P., Marucco, P, Bozzer, C.; Vaj, C., Bradascio, M., Tescari, E., Bosco, V.; Bacci, L., Giberti, A.	
Reference		Atti, Giornate Fitopatologiche, Chianciano Terme (Siena), 18-21 marzo 2014, Volume primo 2014 pp.591-600 ref.3	
DOI			
Country		Italy	
Orchard characteristics	Crop	Vineyard	
	Cultivar	Barbera	
	Row direction	4 x 1	
	Row x Tree spacing (m)	2	
	Total height (m)		
	Skirt (m)	0,7	
	Tree height (m)	1,3	
	Diameter 1 (m)		
	Diameter 2 (m)		
	Canopy volume (m ³) (indicate calculation used)		
	TRV (m ³ TRV/ha)		
	LWA (m ² LWA/ha)		
	BBCH (vineyard)	69/91	
Foliar density/LAI....			
Meteo	Distance/Position of sensors respect the orchard		
	Height 1 (m)= ???	Frequency (Hz)	1
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	✓

3D-orchards

		Horizontal wind direction (°)	✓
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)	
		Temperature (°C)	
		Relative humidity (%)	
		% of measures $\geq 30^\circ$	
		% of measures $\geq 45^\circ$	
	Stability		
Trial layout	Length of passes (row length) (m)		4
	Rows treated (number of rows/ width treated area)		50
	Spray application in the 1st row		
	Substance applied (tracer, PPP,...)	Substance	Tartrazine
		Concentration/Dose	
Treatments	Treatment 1	Sprayer	Airblast sprayer Nobili Geo 1000
		Volume rate (L/ha)	480
		Forward speed (km/h)	4,5
		Airflow (m ³ /h)	30000
		Working pressure (MPa)	0,9
		Type of nozzles	ATR red
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	
Treatments	Treatment 2	Sprayer	Airblast sprayer Nobili Geo 1000
		Volume rate (L/ha)	240
		Forward speed (km/h)	4,5
		Airflow (m ³ /h)	30000
		Working pressure (MPa)	0,9
		Type of nozzles	ATR red
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	
Treatments	Treatment 3	Sprayer	Airblast sprayer Nobili Geo 1000
		Volume rate (L/ha)	480
		Forward speed (km/h)	4,5
		Airflow (m ³ /h)	30000
		Working pressure (MPa)	0,8
		Type of nozzles	TVI 8003
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	
Treatments	Treatment 4	Sprayer	Airblast sprayer Nobili Geo 1000
		Volume rate (L/ha)	240
		Forward speed (km/h)	4,5
		Airflow (m ³ /h)	30000
		Working pressure (MPa)	0,8

3D-orchards

Response variables	Airborne drift	Type of nozzles	TVI 8003
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	
		Collector (if lines, vertical/horizontal)	
		Height range (max-min measured height) (m)	
		Precision (0.5 m/ 1 m...)	
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	
	Sedimenting drift	Replicates/distance	
		Collector	Filter cloth
		Distance range (max-min measured distance) (m)	1-30
		Dimension	200
	Distance/s to the first row (m)	1/30	
	Replicates/distance	6/7	

Notes to Balsari et al. 2014:

Each treatment have been repeated 5 times

6 are the replicate at each distance.

7 are the total number of distances.

These data could not be used to obtain drift curves.

Title	Methodology for Assessment of Drift from Radial Sprayers in Vineyard Applications	
Authors	Y. Gil, C. Sinfort, B. Bonicelli, V. Bellon-Maurel, A. Vallet	
Reference	Information and Technology for Sustainable Fruit and Vegetable Production FRUTIC 05, 12 ñ 16 September 2005 , Montpellier France	
DOI		
Country	France	
Orchard characteristics	Crop	Artificial vineyard
	Cultivar	
	Row direction	
	Row x Tree spacing (m)	2 x 2
	Total height (m)	2

3D-orchards

	Skirt (m)			
	Tree height (m)			
	Diameter 1 (m)			
	Diameter 2 (m)			
	Canopy volume (m ³) (indicate calculation used)			
	TRV (m ³ TRV/ha)			
	LWA (m ² LWA/ha)			
	BBCH (vineyard)			
	Foliar density/LAI....			
Meteo	Distance/Position of sensors respect the orchard		4	
	Height 1 (m)= Wind registred at 2 and 6 meters of height with cup anemometers. At 4 meters a 3D anemometers was placed	Frequency (Hz)		10
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)		✓
		Horizontal wind direction (°)		
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)		
		Temperature (°C)		
		Relative humidity (%)		
		% of measures ≥30°		
% of measures ≥45°				
Stability				
Trial layout	Length of passes (row lenght) (m)		9,5	
	Rows treated (number of rows/ width treated area)		4	
	Spray application in the 1st row			
	Substance applied (tracer, PPP,...)	Substance		Brilliant Sulphoflavine
Concentration/Dose				
Treatments	Treatment 1	Sprayer	Air assisted, axial fan "Fisher type 02 470"	
		Volume rate (L/ha)	114	
		Forward speed (km/h)	5	
		Airflow (m ³ /h)	Low	
		Working pressure (MPa)	1	
		Type of nozzles	ATR White	
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	0,38	
Treatments	Treatment 2	Sprayer	Air assisted, axial fan "Fisher type 02 470"	
		Volume rate (L/ha)	152	
		Forward speed (km/h)	3,75	
		Airflow (m ³ /h)	Medium	
		Working pressure (MPa)	1	
		Type of nozzles	ATR White	
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	0,38	

3D-orchards

Treatments	Treatment 3	Sprayer	Air assisted, axial fan "Fisher type 02 470"
		Volume rate (L/ha)	142,5
		Forward speed (km/h)	4
		Airflow (m3/h)	High
		Working pressure (MPa)	1
		Type of nozzles	ATR White
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	0,38
	Treatment 4	Sprayer	Air assisted, axial fan "Fisher type 02 470"
		Volume rate (L/ha)	300
		Forward speed (km/h)	5
		Airflow (m3/h)	low
		Working pressure (MPa)	1
		Type of nozzles	TKA80015VK
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	1
	Treatment 5	Sprayer	Air assisted, axial fan "Fisher type 02 470"
		Volume rate (L/ha)	400
		Forward speed (km/h)	3,75
		Airflow (m3/h)	Medium
		Working pressure (MPa)	1
		Type of nozzles	TKA80015VK
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	1
	Treatment 6	Sprayer	Air assisted, axial fan "Fisher type 02 470"
		Volume rate (L/ha)	375
		Forward speed (km/h)	4
Airflow (m3/h)		high	
Working pressure (MPa)		1	
Type of nozzles		TKA80015VK	
Liquid flowrate (L/min)		1	
Response variables	Airborne drift	Collector (if lines, vertical/horizontal)	
		Height range (max-min measured height) (m)	
		Precision (0.5 m/ 1 m...)	
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	
		Replicates/distance	
	Sedimenting drift	Collector	

3D-orchards

		Distance range (max-min measured distance) (m)	
		Precision (1 m...)	
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	
		Replicates/distance	

Notes to Gil *et al.* 2005:

A 3D weather station was used but one wind speed is reported on the paper

All the treatment have been conducted operating with one side or two side of the sprayer.

The artificial vineyard consisted of 4 rows (8 x 9,5m). Around the artificial vineyard a "reference box" of 15x15x 5,5 m was located. On each sides of the box 5 PVC lines were placed form 2 to 5,5 m height. In addition, on the box's cover were located two diagonal PVC lines.

These data could not be used to obtain drift curves.

A.4. Articles assessed - OLIVES

Paper info	Paper codename	Godoy-Nieto, 2022	
	Title	Assessment of Spray Deposit and Loss in Traditional and Intensive Olive Orchards with Conventional and Crop-Adapted Sprayers	
	Authors	Godoy-Nieto, A., Miranda-Fuentes, A., Grella, M., Blanco-Roldán, G. L., Rodríguez-Lizana, A., & Gil-Ribes, J. A.	
	Reference	<i>Agronomy</i> , 2022 . 12, 1764	
	Country	Spain	
	DOI	10.3390/agronomy12081764	
Orchard characteristics	Crop		Olive trees
	Cultivar		
	Row direction		
	Row x Tree spacing (m)		7-12 x 7-10
	Crop/tree density (crops/ha or trees/ha)		107 - 204
	Total height (m)		
	Skirt (m)		
	Tree height (m)		
	Diameter 1 (m)		
Diameter 2 (m)			

3D-orchards

	Canopy volume (m3) (indicate calculation used)		
	TRW (m3 TRV/ha)		
	LWA (m2 LWA/ha)		
	BBCH (vineyard)		
	Foliar density/LAI....		
Meteo	Distance/Position of sensors respect the orchard		
	Height 1 (m)=	Frequency (Hz)	0,1
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	0,1
		Horizontal wind direction (°)	235
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)	
		Temperature (°C)	21,5
		Relative humidity (%)	35
		% of measures $\geq 30^\circ$	87,50%
	Height 2 (m) (in case there is)=	% of measures $\geq 45^\circ$	87,50%
		Frequency (Hz)	0,1
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	0,5
		Horizontal wind direction (°)	228
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)	
		Temperature (°C)	23
Relative humidity (%)		35	
% of measures $\geq 30^\circ$	87,50%		
% of measures $\geq 45^\circ$	87,50%		
Stability			
Trial layout	Length of passes (row length) (m)		
	Rows treated (number of rows/ width treated area)		
	Spray application in the 1st row		
	Substance applied (tracer, PPP,...)	Substance	
Concentration/Dose			
Treatment/s	Treatment 1	Sprayer	Conventional airblast sprayer & Air-assisted sprayer prototype
		Volume rate (L/ha)	1057,95
		Forward speed (km/h)	4
		Airflow (m3/h)	31770
		Working pressure (MPa)	1,25
		Type of nozzles	Various
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	39,11
	Treatment 2 (in case)	Sprayer	Conventional airblast sprayer & Air-assisted sprayer prototype

3D-orchards

		Volume rate (L/ha)	1162,3
		Forward speed (km/h)	3
		Airflow (m ³ /h)	44280
		Working pressure (MPa)	1
		Type of nozzles	Various
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	57,67
Response variables	Airborne drift	Collector (if lines, vertical/horizontal)	
		Height range (max-min measured height) (m)	
		Precision (0.5 m/ 1 m...)	
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	
		Replicates/distance	
	Sedimenting drift	Collector	Filter paper
		Distance range (max-min measured distance) (m)	
		Precision (1 m...)	
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	
		Replicates/distance	

Notes to Godoy-Nieto et al., 2022:
Data cannot be used to obtain drift curves.

Paper info	Paper codename	Miranda Fuentes, 2018	
	Title	Reducing spray drift by adapting the spraying equipment to the canopy shape in olive orchards with isolated trees	
	Authors	Miranda Fuentes, A., Cuenca, A., Godoy Nieto, A., González Sánchez, E. J., Gil Moya, E., Llorens, J., & Gil Ribes, J. A.	
	Reference	<i>International Advances in Pesticide Application</i> , 2018 . 325-332.	
	Country	Spain	
	DOI	N/A	
Orchard characteristics	Crop	Olive trees	
	Cultivar		
	Row direction		
	Row x Tree spacing (m)	7 x - (int.) & 10 x 12 (trad.)	
	Crop/tree density (crops/ha or trees/ha)	204 (intens.) & 107 (trad.)	
	Total height (m)		
	Skirt (m)		
Tree height (m)	3.54 (intens.) & 4.82 (trad.)		

3D-orchards

	Diameter 1 (m)		
	Diameter 2 (m)		
	Canopy volume (m ³) (indicate calculation used)		23.86 (intens.) & 90.34 (trad.)
	TRW (m ³ TRV/ha)		
	LWA (m ² LWA/ha)		
	BBCH (vineyard)		
	Foliar density/LAI...		
Meteo	Distance/Position of sensors respect the orchard		
	Height 1 (m)=	Frequency (Hz)	0,1
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	< 0.3
		Horizontal wind direction (°)	
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)	
		Temperature (°C)	21,5
		Relative humidity (%)	45
		% of measures ≥30°	
	Height 2 (m) (in case there is)=	Frequency (Hz)	0,1
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	< 0.3
		Horizontal wind direction (°)	
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)	
		Temperature (°C)	26,5
		Relative humidity (%)	52
% of measures ≥30°			
Stability			
Trial layout	Length of passes (row lenght) (m)		
	Rows treated (number of rows/ width treated area)		
	Spray application in the 1st row		
	Substance applied (tracer, PPP,...)	Substance	Tartrazine
	Concentration/Dose	8 g/l	
Treatment/s	Treatment 1	Sprayer	Conventional airblast sprayer & Air-assisted sprayer prototype
		Volume rate (L/ha)	584,05
		Forward speed (km/h)	4
		Airflow (m ³ /h)	39060
		Working pressure (MPa)	1,2
		Type of nozzles	Perimeter hollow cone nozzles
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	38,79

3D-orchards

	Treatment 2 (in case)	Sprayer	Conventional airblast sprayer & Air-assisted sprayer prototype
		Volume rate (L/ha)	1161,05
		Forward speed (km/h)	2,95
		Airflow (m ³ /h)	44280
		Working pressure (MPa)	1,05
		Type of nozzles	Various
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	57,09
Response variables	Airborne drift	Collector (if lines, vertical/horizontal)	Filter paper
		Height range (max-min measured height) (m)	
		Precision (0.5 m/ 1 m...)	
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	
		Replicates/distance	
	Sedimenting drift	Collector	Petri dishes
		Distance range (max-min measured distance) (m)	
		Precision (1 m...)	
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	
		Replicates/distance	

Notes to Miranda-Fuentes et al., 2018:
Data cannot be used to obtain drift curves.

Paper info	Paper codename	Solanelles, 2006	
	Title	An electronic control system for pesticide application proportional to the canopy width of tree crops	
	Authors	Solanelles, F., Escolà, A., Planas, S., Rosell, J. R., Camp, F., & Gràcia, F.	
	Reference	<i>Biosystems engineering</i> , 2006. 95(4), 473	
	Country	Spain	
	DOI	10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2006.08.004	
Orchard characteristics	Crop	Olive trees	
	Cultivar	Arbequina	
	Row direction		
	Row x Tree spacing (m)	5 x 4	
	Crop/tree density (crops/ha or trees/ha)		
Total height (m)			

3D-orchards

	Skirt (m)		
	Tree height (m)		
	Diameter 1 (m)		
	Diameter 2 (m)		
	Canopy volume (m3) (indicate calculation used)		
	TRW (m3 TRV/ha)		
	LWA (m2 LWA/ha)		
	BBCH (vineyard)		
	Foliar density/LAI...		
Meteo	Distance/Position of sensors respect the orchard		
	Height 1 (m)=	Frequency (Hz)	10
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	1.8 - 2.7
		Horizontal wind direction (°)	30 - 44
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)	
		Temperature (°C)	13.6 - 14.7
		Relative humidity (%)	49.8 - 52.4
		% of measures ≥30°	
	% of measures ≥45°		
	Height 2 (m) (in case there is)=	Frequency (Hz)	
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	
		Horizontal wind direction (°)	
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)	
		Temperature (°C)	
		Relative humidity (%)	
% of measures ≥30°			
% of measures ≥45°			
Stability			
Trial layout	Length of passes (row length) (m)		
	Rows treated (number of rows/ width treated area)		
	Spray application in the 1st row		
	Substance applied (tracer, PPP,...)	Substance	Metal chelates (Fe, Zn and Mn)
	Concentration/Dose	2-3 g/l	
Treatment/s	Treatment 1	Sprayer	Air-assisted prototype sprayer
		Volume rate (L/ha)	520
		Forward speed (km/h)	2,88
		Airflow (m3/h)	
		Working pressure (MPa)	0,8
		Type of nozzles	Yellow and orange Albuz

3D-orchards

		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	5
	Treatment 2 (in case)	Sprayer	
		Volume rate (L/ha)	
		Forward speed (km/h)	
		Airflow (m ³ /h)	
		Working pressure (MPa)	
		Type of nozzles	
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	
Response variables		Airborne drift	Collector (if lines, vertical/horizontal)
	Height range (max-min measured height) (m)		10
	Precision (0.5 m/ 1 m...)		0,5
	Distance/s to the first row (m)		
	Replicates/distance		
	Sedimenting drift	Collector	Filter paper
		Distance range (max-min measured distance) (m)	
		Precision (1 m...)	
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	
		Replicates/distance	

Notes to Solanelles et al., 2006:**Data cannot be used to obtain drift curves.**

Paper info	Paper codename	Solanelles, 2002	
	Title	Spray application efficiency of an electronic control system for proportional application to the canopy volume	
	Authors	Solanelles, F., Planas, S., Escola, A., & Rosell, J. R.	
	Reference	<i>Applied Biology</i> , 2002. 66, 139.	
	Country	Spain	
	DOI		
Orchard characteristics	Crop	Olive trees	
	Cultivar	Arbequina	
	Row direction		
	Row x Tree spacing (m)	5 x 4	
	Crop/tree density (crops/ha or trees/ha)		
	Total height (m)		
	Skirt (m)		

3D-orchards

	Tree height (m)		
	Diameter 1 (m)		
	Diameter 2 (m)		
	Canopy volume (m3) (indicate calculation used)		
	TRW (m3 TRV/ha)		
	LWA (m2 LWA/ha)		
	BBCH (vineyard)		
	Foliar density/LAI...		
Meteo	Distance/Position of sensors respect the orchard		
	Height 1 (m)=	Frequency (Hz)	
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	1.8 - 2.7
		Horizontal wind direction (°)	30 - 44
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)	
		Temperature (°C)	13.6 - 14.7
		Relative humidity (%)	49.8 - 52.4
		% of measures ≥30°	
	Height 2 (m) (in case there is)=	Frequency (Hz)	
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	
		Horizontal wind direction (°)	
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)	
		Temperature (°C)	
		Relative humidity (%)	
% of measures ≥45°			
Stability			
Trial layout	Length of passes (row length) (m)		
	Rows treated (number of rows/ width treated area)		
	Spray application in the 1st row		
	Substance applied (tracer, PPP,...)	Substance	Metal chelates (Fe, Zn and Mn)
Treatment/s	Treatment 1	Concentration/Dose	3 g/l
		Sprayer	Air-assisted prototype sprayer
		Volume rate (L/ha)	520
		Forward speed (km/h)	3
		Airflow (m3/h)	
		Working pressure (MPa)	1
		Type of nozzles	Albuz ATR Yellow
Liquid flowrate (L/min)			

3D-orchards

	Treatment 2 (in case)	Sprayer	
		Volume rate (L/ha)	
		Forward speed (km/h)	
		Airflow (m ³ /h)	
		Working pressure (MPa)	
		Type of nozzles	
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	
Response variables	Airborne drift	Collector (if lines, vertical/horizontal)	
		Height range (max-min measured height) (m)	10
		Precision (0.5 m/ 1 m...)	0,5
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	
		Replicates/distance	
	Sedimenting drift	Collector	Filter paper
		Distance range (max-min measured distance) (m)	
		Precision (1 m...)	
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	
		Replicates/distance	

Notes to Solanelles *et al.*, 2002:
Data cannot be used to obtain drift curves.

Paper info	Paper codename	Gil, 2018
	Title	First attempts to obtain a reference drift curve for traditional olive grove's plantations following ISO 22866
	Authors	Gil, E., Llorens, J., Gallart, M., Gil-Ribes, J. A., & Miranda-Fuentes, A.
	Reference	<i>Science of the total environment</i> , 2018 . 627, 349.
	Country	Spain
	DOI	
Orchard characteristics	Crop	Olive trees
	Cultivar	Picual and Hojiblanca
	Row direction	
	Row x Tree spacing (m)	12 x 12
	Crop/tree density (crops/ha or trees/ha)	
	Total height (m)	
	Skirt (m)	
Tree height (m)	4.1 - 5 (mean: 4.66)	

3D-orchards

	Diameter 1 (m)		
	Diameter 2 (m)		
	Canopy volume (m3) (indicate calculation used)	27.47 - 110.72 (mean: 61.88) (LiDAR)	
	TRW (m3 TRV/ha)		
	LWA (m2 LWA/ha)		
	BBCH (vineyard)		
	Foliar density/LAI...		
Meteo	Distance/Position of sensors respect the orchard		
	Height 1 (m)=	Frequency (Hz)	
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	1.06 - 2.28
		Horizontal wind direction (°)	19.55 - 57.95
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)	
		Temperature (°C)	10.72 - 16.45
		Relative humidity (%)	32.34 - 64.46
		% of measures $\geq 30^\circ$	
	Height 2 (m) (in case there is)=	Frequency (Hz)	
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	
		Horizontal wind direction (°)	
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)	
		Temperature (°C)	10.45 - 16.33
		Relative humidity (%)	32.64 - 65.45
% of measures $\geq 30^\circ$			
Stability			
Trial layout	Length of passes (row length) (m)		
	Rows treated (number of rows/ width treated area)		
	Spray application in the 1st row		
	Substance applied (tracer, PPP,...)	Substance Concentration/Dose	Tartrazine
Treatment/s	Treatment 1	Sprayer	Airblast sprayer with an axial fan
		Volume rate (L/ha)	1008
		Forward speed (km/h)	2,85
		Airflow (m3/h)	33840
		Working pressure (MPa)	1
		Type of nozzles	Albus ATR Blue
	Liquid flowrate (L/min)	47,8	
Treatment 2 (in case)	Sprayer		

3D-orchards

		Volume rate (L/ha)	
		Forward speed (km/h)	
		Airflow (m ³ /h)	
		Working pressure (MPa)	
		Type of nozzles	
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	
Response variables	Airborne drift	Collector (if lines, vertical/horizontal)	masts containing airborne collectors
		Height range (max-min measured height) (m)	max. 6m
		Precision (0.5 m/ 1 m...)	
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	5m and 10m
		Replicates/distance	2
	Sedimenting drift	Collector	Petri dishes
		Distance range (max-min measured distance) (m)	1 - 20m
		Precision (1 m...)	1 - 5m
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	3
		Replicates/distance	

Notes to Gil et al., 2018:

Data could be used to obtain drift curves.

A.5. Articles assessed - CITRUS

Title	Studies on pesticide spray drift in a Mediterranean citrus area				
Authors	S.M. MELI, A. RENDA, M. NICELLI, E. CAPRI				
Reference	<i>Agronomie</i> 2003. 23, 667				
DOI	10.1051/agro:2003044				
Country	Italy (Catania)				
Orchard characteristics	Crop	Citrus orchards			
	Cultivar	T1&T2 Tarocco nucellare orange	T3&T4 Tardivo di Ciaculli mandarin	T5&T6 Navelina nucellare sour orange	T7&T8 Tarocco comune sour orange
	Row direction	N - S	N - S	NE - SW	W - E
	Row x Tree spacing (m)	6 x 5	4 x 4	6 x 4	6 x 4
	Total height (m)				
Skirt (m)					

3D-orchards

	Tree height (m)	5	2,3	3,3	2,5
	Diameter 1 (m)	5	4	4,8	3,8
	Diameter 2 (m)	5,3	4	4	3,5
	Canopy volume (m ³)				
	TRV (m ³ TRV/ha)				
	LWA (m ² LWA/ha)				
	BBCH (vineyard)				
	Foliar density/LAI....				
Meteo	Distance/Position of sensors respect the orchard				
	Height 1 (m)= 2 m	Frequency (Hz)	0,003		
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	✓		
		Horizontal wind direction (°)	✓		
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)			
		Temperature (°C)	✓		
		Relative humidity (%)			
		% of measures ≥30°			
% of measures ≥45°					
	Stability				
Trial layout	Length of passes (row length) (m)				
	Rows treated (number of rows/ width treated area)				
	Spray application in the 1st row				
	Substance applied (tracer, PPP,...)	Substance	Chlorpyrifos-methyl		
Concentration/Dose		0,563 g/L			
Treatment/s	T1	Sprayer	Manual lance		
		Volume rate (L/ha)	3194		
		Forward speed (km/h)			
		Airflow (m ³ /h)			
		Working pressure (MPa)	2,5		
		Type of nozzles	VOLPI E BOTTOLI High Pressure Hollow Cone nozzle (1.5 mm ø)		
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	4,5		
	T2	Sprayer	Fan-assisted		

3D-orchards

		Volume rate (L/ha)	3353			
		Forward speed (km/h)				
		Airflow (m ³ /h)				
		Working pressure (MPa)	2 - 3			
		Type of nozzles	ALBUZ High Pressure Hollow Cone nozzles			
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	3,9 -5,9			
	T3	Sprayer	Manual lance			
		Volume rate (L/ha)	2609			
		Forward speed (km/h)				
		Airflow (m ³ /h)				
		Working pressure (MPa)	2,5			
		Type of nozzles	VOLPI E BOTTOLI High Pressure Hollow Cone nozzle (1.5 mm ø)			
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	4,5			
	T4	Sprayer	Fan-assisted			
		Volume rate (L/ha)	2676			
		Forward speed (km/h)				
		Airflow (m ³ /h)				
		Working pressure (MPa)	2 - 3			
		Type of nozzles	ALBUZ High Pressure Hollow Cone nozzles			
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	2,6			
	T5	Sprayer	Manual lance			
		Volume rate (L/ha)	2825			
		Forward speed (km/h)				
		Airflow (m ³ /h)				
		Working pressure (MPa)	2,5			
		Type of nozzles	VOLPI E BOTTOLI High Pressure Hollow Cone nozzle (1.5 mm ø)			

3D-orchards

	T6	Liquid flowrate (L/min)	4,5			
		Sprayer	Fan-assisted			
		Volume rate (L/ha)	2900			
		Forward speed (km/h)				
		Airflow (m3/h)				
		Working pressure (MPa)	2 - 3			
		Type of nozzles	ALBUZ High Pressure Hollow Cone nozzles			
	Liquid flowrate (L/min)	3,1				
	T7	Sprayer	Manual lance			
		Volume rate (L/ha)	2262			
		Forward speed (km/h)				
		Airflow (m3/h)				
		Working pressure (MPa)	2,5			
		Type of nozzles	VOLPI E BOTTOLI High Pressure Hollow Cone nozzle (1.5 mm ø)			
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	4,5			
	T8	Sprayer	Fan-assisted			
		Volume rate (L/ha)	2516			
		Forward speed (km/h)				
		Airflow (m3/h)				
		Working pressure (MPa)	2 - 3			
		Type of nozzles	ALBUZ High Pressure Hollow Cone nozzles			
Liquid flowrate (L/min)		3				
Response variables	Airborne drift	Collector (if lines, vertical/horizontal)				
		Height range (max-min measured height) (m)				
		Precision (0.5 m/ 1 m...)				
		Distance/s to the first row (m)				
		Replicates/distance				

3D-orchards

	Sedimenting drift	Collector	Filter paper lines (chromatographic paper) 5 cm wide			
		Distance range (max-min measured distance) (m)	1.5-7.5			
		Precision (1 m...)	1,5			
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	1,5			
		Replicates/distance	1			

Notes to Meli et al. 2003:

Deposition drift was measured only at following distance from the orchard edge of 1.5, 3, 4.5, 6 and 7.5 m. 1 application with each sprayer (manual lance and fan-assisted) in each orchard, in a total of 4 orchards. No repetitions of applications per orchard were done.

Data could be used to obtain drift curves but only at short distances (from 1.5-7.5 m).

Title		Chlorpyrifos-methyl dissipation in a small adjacent water body following application to citrus	
Authors		L. Padovani, E. Capri	
Reference		<i>Chemosphere</i> 2005. 58, 1219	
DOI		10.1016/j.chemosphere.2004.09.035	
Country		Italy (Catania)	
Orchard characteristics	Crop	Citrus orchards	
	Cultivar	Tarocco comune sour orange	
	Row direction	N-S	
	Row x Tree spacing (m)	6 x 4	
	Total height (m)	2,5	
	Skirt (m)		
	Tree height (m)		
	Diameter 1 (m)		
	Diameter 2 (m)		
	Canopy volume (m3) (indicate calculation used)		
	TRV (m3 TRV/ha)		
	LWA (m2 LWA/ha)		
	BBCH (vineyard)		
Foliar density/LAI...			

3D-orchards

Meteo	Distance/Position of sensors respect the orchard			
	Height 1 (m)= ??	Frequency (Hz)		
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	✓	
		Horizontal wind direction (°)	✓	
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)		
		Temperature (°C)	✓	
		Relative humidity (%)		
		% of measures $\geq 30^\circ$		
		% of measures $\geq 45^\circ$		
Stability				
Trial layout	Length of passes (row length) (m)			
	Rows treated (number of rows/ width treated area)		6768 m2	
	Spray application in the 1st row			
	Substance applied (tracer, PPP,...)	Substance	Chlorpyrifos-methyl	
Concentration/Dose		1,238 kg/ha		
Treatment/s	Treatment	Sprayer	Fan-driven sprayer	
		Volume rate (L/ha)	220	149 L / 0,6768 ha
		Forward speed (km/h)	0,7	
		Airflow (m3/h)		
		Working pressure (MPa)	3	
		Type of nozzles	ALBUZ high pressure hollow cone nozzles	
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	4	
		Response variables	Airborne drift	Collector (if lines, vertical/horizontal)
Height range (max-min measured height) (m)				
Precision (0.5 m/ 1 m...)				
Distance/s to the first row (m)				
Replicates/distance				
Sedimenting drift	Collector			Horizontal
	Distance range (max-min measured distance) (m)			
	Precision (1 m...)			
	Distance/s to the first row (m)		0	
	Replicates/distance			

Notes to Padovani 2005:

The collectors' line was in line with the tree rows, not perpendicular.

Data could not be used to obtain drift curves.

Title		Exposure of surface water bodies to chlorpyrifos and chlorpyrifos-methyl in the Mediterranean area	
Authors		Salvatore Marco Meli, Ettore Capri and Mara Gennari	
Reference		Fresenius Environmental Bulletin Volume 16 – No 1. 2007: 50-56	
DOI		(THERE IS NO DOI)	
Country		Italy (Catania)	
Orchard characteristics	Crop	Citrus orchards	
	Cultivar	Tarocco comune sour orange	
	Row direction	N - S	
	Row x Tree spacing (m)	6 x 4	
	Total height (m)		
	Skirt (m)		
	Tree height (m)	2,5	
	Diameter 1 (m)	8 m2 (Crown projection)	
	Diameter 2 (m)		
	Canopy volume (m3) (indicate calculation used)	10,47	
	TRV (m3 TRV/ha)		
	LWA (m2 LWA/ha)		
	BBCH (vineyard)		
Foliar density/LAI....	✓		
Meteo	Distance/Position of sensors respect the orchard		
	Height 1 (m)= 2 m	Frequency (Hz)	0,003
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	0,6
		Horizontal wind direction (°)	(49°) NE - SW
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)	
		Temperature (°C)	29,9 -25,1
		Relative humidity (%)	
		% of measures ≥30°	
	Stability		
	Trial layout	Length of passes (row lenght) (m)	
Rows treated (number of rows/ width treated area)			

3D-orchards

	Spray application in the 1st row		
	Substance applied (tracer, PPP,...)	Substance	Chlorpyrifos-methyl
		Concentration/Dose	0,563 g/L
Treatment/s	Treatment	Sprayer	Turbo fan driven sprayer
		Volume rate (L/ha)	2260
		Forward speed (km/h)	0,7
		Airflow (m ³ /h)	
		Working pressure (MPa)	3
		Type of nozzles	ALBUZ High Pressure Hollow Cone nozzles
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	6,3
Response variables	Airborne drift	Collector (if lines, vertical/horizontal)	
		Height range (max-min measured height) (m)	
		Precision (0.5 m/ 1 m...)	
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	
		Replicates/distance	
	Sedimenting drift	Collector	Chromatographic paper
		Distance range (max-min measured distance) (m)	
		Precision (1 m...)	
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	
		Replicates/distance	

Notes to Meli et al. 2007:

The collectors' line was in line with the tree rows, not perpendicular.

Data could not be used to obtain drift curves.

Title	Comparison between standard and drift reducing nozzles for pesticide application in citrus: Part I. Effects on wind tunnel and field spray drift	
Authors	Xavier Torrent, Cruz Garcerá, Enrique Moltó, Patricia Chueca, Raquel Abad, Carmen Grafulla, Carla Román, Santiago Planas	
Reference	<i>Crop Protection</i> 2017. 96, 130	
DOI	http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.cropro.2017.02.001	
Country	Spain	

3D-orchards

		Location 1: Roquetes (SP)	Location 2: Montserrat (SP)	
Orchard characteristics	Crop	Citrus orchards	Citrus orchards	
	Cultivar	Clementine cv. Clemenules	Clementine cv. Clemenules	
	Row direction	E-W	N-S	
	Row x Tree spacing (m)	6.00 x 4.00	5.00 x 3.50	
	Total height (m)	2,85	2,75	
	Skirt (m)	0	0,15	
	Tree height (m)	2,83	2,6	
	Diameter 1 (m)	2,8	2,9	
	Diameter 2 (m)	2,5	3,7	
	Canopy volume (m ³) (indicate calculation used)	10.40 (Ellipsoid)	14.60 (Ellipsoid)	
	TRV (m ³ TRV/ha)			
	LWA (m ² LWA/ha)			
	BBCH (vineyard)			
Foliar density/LAI....				
Meteo	Distance/Position of sensors respect the orchard		50 m	50 m
	Height (m)= 7	Frequency (Hz)	1	1
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	✓	✓
		Horizontal wind direction (°)	✓	✓
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)		
		Temperature (°C)	✓	✓
		Relative humidity (%)	✓	✓
		% of measures ≥30°		
		% of measures ≥45°	✓	✓
Stability				
Trial layout	Length of passes (row length) (m)		50 m	50 m
	Rows treated (number of rows/ width treated area)		4	4
	Spray application in the 1st row		Only towards the orchard	Only towards the orchard
	Substance applied (tracer, PPP,...)	Substance	Water and a fluorescent tracer, brilliant sulphoflavine.	Water and a fluorescent tracer, brilliant sulphoflavine.
		Concentration/Dose	1 g/L	1 g/L

3D-orchards

Treatment/s	Treatment 1 (5 replicates/location)	Sprayer	Axial fan airblaster	
		Volume rate (L/ha)	2456	2550
		Forward speed (km/h)	1	1,58
		Airflow (m3/h)	29700	69700
		Working pressure (MPa)	1,5	1
		Type of nozzles	Standard Hollow cone (Albuz ATR)	Standard Hollow cone (Teejet Disc and core)
	Liquid flowrate (L/min)			
	Treatment 2 (5 replicates/location)	Sprayer	Axial fan airblaster	
		Volume rate (L/ha)	2388	2713
		Forward speed (km/h)	1	1,58
		Airflow (m3/h)	29700	69700
		Working pressure (MPa)	1,3	1
Type of nozzles		Low drift Albuz TVI	Low drift Albuz TVI	
Liquid flowrate (L/min)				
Response variables	Airborne drift	Collector (if lines, vertical/horizontal)	Vertical nylon threads (2 mm)	Vertical nylon threads (2 mm)
		Height range (max-min measured height) (m)	1 - 6	1 - 6
		Precision (0.5 m/ 1 m...)	1	1
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	5 & 10	5 & 10
		Replicates/distance	2 (2 m apart)	2 (2 m apart)
	Sedimenting drift	Collector	Horizontal blotting papers	Horizontal blotting papers
		Distance range (max-min measured distance) (m)	1.5 - 40	1.5 - 40
		Precision (1 m...)	2.5 & 5	2.5 & 5
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	1,5	1,5
		Replicates/distance	3 (1.5 m apart)	3 (1.5 m apart)

Notes to Torrent *et al.* 2017:

Airborne and sedimenting drift were measured for airblast treatments at citrus comparing conventional and drift reduction nozzles. (2 treatments). The assays were done in 2 locations (Montserrat and Roquetes). 5 replicates per treatment and location was done

Data could be used to obtain drift curves.

3D-orchards

Title		Spray pesticide applications in Mediterranean citrus orchards: Canopy deposition and off-target losses	
Authors		Cruz Garcerá, Enrique Moltó, Patricia Chueca	
Reference		<i>Science of the Total Environment</i> 2017. 599–600, 344	
DOI		http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.05.029	
Country		Spain	
Orchard characteristics	Crop	Citrus orchards	
	Cultivar	Navel orange	
	Row direction		
	Row x Tree spacing (m)	6 x 4	
	Total height (m)	2,65	
	Skirt (m)	0	
	Tree height (m)	2,65	
	Diameter 1 (m)	3,6	
	Diameter 2 (m)	3,83	
	Canopy volume (m3) (indicate calculation used)	19,23	
	TRV (m3 TRV/ha)		
	LWA (m2 LWA/ha)		
	BBCH (vineyard)		
Foliar density/LAI....			
Meteo	Distance/Position of sensors respect the orchard		54 m
	Height 1 (m)= 7	Frequency (Hz)	1
		Horizontal wind speed (m/s)	✓
		Horizontal wind direction (°)	✓
		Vertical wind speed (m/s)	✓
		Temperature (°C)	✓
		Relative humidity (%)	✓
		% of measures ≥30°	
		% of measures ≥45°	
Stability			
Trial layout	Length of passes (row length) (m)		20
	Rows treated (number of rows/ width treated area)		1
	Spray application in the 1st row		
	Substance applied (tracer, PPP,...)	Substance	Water and a fluorescent tracer, brilliant sulphoflavine.
	Concentration/Dose	1 g / l	
Treatments	Treatment 1	Sprayer	Axial fan airblaster
		Volume rate (L/ha)	2930

3D-orchards

		Forward speed (km/h)	1,656
		Airflow (m ³ /h)	86400
		Working pressure (MPa)	1
		Type of nozzles	STN TeeJet D3-DC35
		Liquid flowrate (L/min)	2
	Treatment 2	Sprayer	Axial fan airblaster
	Volume rate (L/ha)	3206	
	Forward speed (km/h)	1,656	
	Airflow (m ³ /h)	86400	
	Working pressure (MPa)	1	
Type of nozzles	DRN Albus TVI 80 03		
Liquid flowrate (L/min)	2,9		
Response variables	Airborne drift	Collector (if lines, vertical/horizontal)	Horizontal
		Height range (max-min measured height) (m)	5 maximum
		Precision (0.5 m/ 1 m...)	0,1
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	0
		Replicates/distance	Each row
	Sedimenting drift	Collector	
		Distance range (max-min measured distance) (m)	0 - 30
		Precision (1 m...)	
		Distance/s to the first row (m)	0
		Replicates/distance	Each row

Notes to Garcerá *et al.* 2017:

These trials were aimed at quantifying the mass balance during pesticide applications in citrus, therefore ISO 22866 was not followed and measurements were done inside the orchard (attached a figure with the sketch of the orchard and the location of collectors).

These data could not be used to obtain drift curves.